

PhDs and Paychecks: Exploring the Financial Returns of Doctoral Education in Germany's Workforce

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Abstract

While numerous studies have demonstrated that higher educational qualifications are associated with increased income, the specific financial benefits of holding a doctoral degree (PhD) remain less well understood. Due to the relatively small proportion of PhD holders in the general population, most empirical studies face challenges in estimating precise effects. Using extensive official German *Mikrozensus* data—including over 160,000 employees with some form of tertiary education (7.3% with a PhD; 37% female; median age 41)—from four survey rounds between 2018 and 2022, this study provides new insights. On average, salaried employees with a PhD earn 26.8% more than those with a master's degree. After adjusting for factors such as occupational field and working hours, this premium decreases to approximately 11.7%, yet remains substantial. The financial advantage of a PhD is rather similar for men and women, with adjusted premiums of 13% and 10%, respectively. Decomposition analyses show that nearly half (48.4%) of the earnings premium can be attributed to differences in occupational roles, longer working hours, greater likelihood of holding leadership positions, and employment in larger organizations. The occupational fields with the highest adjusted PhD premiums—reaching up to 27%—are Finance, Legal, and Health professions. In sum, based on high-quality data, these findings provide robust evidence of the extent and underlying mechanisms through which PhD holders benefit financially from their advanced and prestigious qualifications.

Keywords:

tertiary education, phd, income, wages, gender, decomposition, Germany

1. Introduction

Germany is known to be one of Europe's biggest producers of doctoral graduates (Cyranoski et al., 2011). On average, 27,000 people get to place the prestigious "Dr." before their names every year (BuWiK, 2025, p.98). This fact raises the question of why there is such a great interest in the prestigious degree. Germany certainly offers excellent research infrastructure, with a long history of outstanding and innovative research and a dense network of universities across the country (Watson, 2010). However, there must be additional advantages to obtaining a doctorate. While prestige and access to certain positions (especially in research and academia) are measurable benefits, the monetary rewards should not be overlooked. Indeed, numerous studies demonstrate wage premiums and other positive occupational outcomes for PhD graduates, making the pursuit of a doctoral degree appear both rational and justified.

Most previous studies draw on the DZHW graduate panel (Vietgen et al., 2020), a prospective survey that began in 2006. While these data are unmatched in providing insights into individual graduate trajectories and are well-suited for addressing causal questions, the panel's relatively small number of respondents and limited observation window mean that many research questions remain unanswered. In particular, analyses offering more detailed insights at the occupational level or examining wages after several years in the labor market are difficult to conduct. Although highly valuable, these panel data cannot address all relevant questions. To obtain a more representative picture of the situation in Germany as a whole, additional data sources are needed. For example, it is important to ask: In which occupations do graduates benefit most from their degrees compared to other holders of tertiary qualifications? Furthermore, when such benefits exist, what explains them? What makes PhD graduates particularly valuable to employers? The following analyses draw on official

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data sources, which not only include a rich set of variables and a very large number of respondents ($N > 160,000$) but also provide information on PhD graduates of all ages and career stages. In summary, we address the following research questions: (1) Do individuals with a PhD earn more than those with lower academic degrees (master's or bachelor's)? (2) Is the monetary benefit of a PhD identical for men and women, or do differences exist? (3) Which factors help explain why individuals with a PhD earn higher incomes than those without? (4) For which occupations is holding a PhD especially advantageous in terms of financial rewards?

2. Theoretical framework

2.1. State of research

Since the early 1990s, the global number of individuals obtaining doctoral degrees has steadily increased (Auriol, 2010). Among the countries with the highest number of doctorate recipients is Germany. Compared to other countries, Germany has a high doctoral attainment rate, measured as the proportion of an age cohort pursuing a doctorate. While the OECD average stands at 1.3% (ages 25-64), Germany reaches 1.9%, placing it among the leading countries (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, 2023). As of 2023, over 200,000 students were enrolled in doctoral programs at German universities with the legal authority to award doctoral degrees ("Promotionsrecht"). Between 2010 and 2022, the annual number of completed doctorates rose by 8%, from 25,629 in 2010 to 27,692 in 2022 (BuWiK, 2025, p.94-96). The increase in the number of doctorates awarded over the past two decades can be attributed solely to the growing participation of women (Auer et al., 2017, p.18).

In Germany, only a relatively small proportion of doctorate holders pursue academic careers compared to other higher education systems. On average, nearly two-thirds of doctorate holders leave academia for positions in the public or private sector (Auer et al., 2017, p.19). The doctorate thus plays a crucial role in supplying highly skilled professionals to industry and public administration (Mertens and Röbbken, 2013, p.218). By international standards, the German doctorate not only serves as a qualification for academic careers but also enjoys high recognition and prestige beyond the academic system (Auer et al., 2017, p.19).

Although the economic and societal contributions of highly qualified graduates to modern knowledge societies are widely acknowledged (Auriol 2010), the individual returns to doctoral education remain comparatively under-researched. Considering the rising number of doctorate holders, the question arises as to what extent earning a doctorate in Germany leads to higher monetary returns and which mechanisms influ-

ence these outcomes. In terms of wage premiums, most studies indicate that individuals with a doctorate benefit from their higher qualifications compared to non-doctorate holders (Germany: Heineck and Matthes (2012); Mertens and Röbbken (2013); Falk and Küpper (2013); Flöther (2015); Trennt and Euler (2019); Euler and Trennt (2024)).¹

A recent study on Germany by Euler and Trennt (2024) shows that individuals with a PhD generally earn higher gross hourly wages than those without a doctoral degree. This wage premium remains consistent across employment sectors and graduation cohorts. Despite the growing number of PhD holders entering the labor market over the past decade, relative wage returns have not declined. In line with previous research (e.g., Heineck and Matthes (2012); Falk and Küpper (2013)), the study finds no significant income advantage for PhD holders in the public sector, whereas a consistent wage premium is observed for those employed in the private sector. The wage premium for doctoral graduates varies not only by sector but also by gender. Previous studies have shown that female PhD holders earn significantly less than their male counterparts, even after controlling for various factors (Bornmann and Enders, 2004; Engelage and Hadjar, 2008; Schulze, 2015). For Germany, Goldan (2021) finds that, two years after graduation, female PhD holders in Germany earn on average 27.2% less than their male counterparts—a gap only partly explained by observable factors, with the remainder potentially reflecting discrimination and structural labor market dynamics.

In Germany, income differences between PhD and non-PhD holders have mostly been examined using relatively small datasets such as the DZHW-Absolventenpanel (e.g., Trennt and Euler (2019); Euler and Trennt (2024)) or various other graduate surveys like the HIS-Absolventenpanel (e.g., Heineck and Matthes (2012); Fabian (2013)). While these datasets contain rich information for studying causal mechanisms, they are limited by relatively small sample sizes and a restricted window of observation.

Only a few studies have so far made use of the large-scale *Mikrozensus*, which is very likely the largest dataset available to researchers regarding educational outcomes in Germany. For example, Mertens and Röbbken (2013), using *Mikrozensus* data from 2006, found substantial income premiums for doctoral degree holders, even after controlling for demographic and job-related characteristics. On average, the return on a PhD was estimated at 5.4%. However, the income gains from earning a doctorate varied considerably across fields of study (not occupations in the labor market). While doctorate holders in education showed only a modest increase

¹Auer et al. (2017) provides a good overview of the relevant international studies, most of which also point to higher earnings for PhD holders compared to non-PhD holders. An interesting exception is Pedersen (2016), who finds no wage premium for phd holders in the danish private sector.

of 2.6%, individuals with PhDs in law and economics experienced significantly higher income gains of around 14%. Although examining income differences by field of study yields important insights into discipline-specific returns, this perspective can misrepresent actual labor market outcomes because many individuals work outside their trained discipline and substantial variation exists within a single field. Apart from [Mertens and Röbbken \(2013\)](#), only [Wienert \(2006\)](#) has used *Mikrozensus* data to examine the financial returns to a PhD in Germany. However, both studies are based on data almost 20 years old. In our analysis, we draw on the most recent *Mikrozensus* rounds (up to 2022), pooling four years of data to increase statistical power. Unlike Mertens and Röbbken, we categorize respondents according to occupational fields using the ISCO-08 classification. This approach has the advantage of capturing individuals' actual labor market positions and linking income differences to job-specific characteristics, which are often more closely associated with earnings than the field of study. In addition, we conduct a decomposition analysis to understand which factors explain the potential income differences between individuals with and without a doctorate, and which share of the variance remains unexplained.

2.2. Theoretical explanations and hypotheses

The positive relationship between education and wages is well established: on average, each additional year of education is associated with higher earnings, and college-educated individuals enjoy greater labor market returns than their less-educated peers (OECD, 2023). However, the mechanisms underlying this education–wage linkage remain contested ([Wouterse et al., 2017](#); [van de Werfhorst, 2011](#)). Economists have traditionally emphasized human capital ([Becker, 1964](#)) and signaling theory ([Spence, 1973](#)) to explain why higher levels of education translate into higher pay. According to classical human capital theory (HCT; Becker, 1964), education enhances individuals' skills and competencies relevant to productive activities, thereby increasing their labor market productivity and, in turn, their wages. Human capital theory treats education as an investment with expected returns in the form of higher lifetime earnings. From this perspective, completing a PhD increases productivity through enhanced knowledge and skills, which should lead to higher wages that offset the time, costs, and foregone earnings during study ([Mertens and Röbbken, 2013](#); [Wouterse et al., 2017](#)). Signaling theory offers a different explanation, viewing the doctorate as a credible signal of exceptional ability, perseverance, and problem-solving capacity—qualities employers may reward even if they do not directly increase productivity

([Spence, 1973](#)). [Franck and Opitz \(2004\)](#) argue that, in Germany, the doctorate serves as a more important talent signal than in countries such as France or the United States, partly because student selection at German universities is less stringent.

In contrast, credentialist theories ([Collins, 1979](#)) emphasize the function of educational qualifications as mechanisms of social closure and stratification. From this perspective, the PhD frequently operates as a formal entry requirement for high-status or highly compensated positions, with the resulting wage premium reflecting institutional gatekeeping rather than differences in individual skills. This logic is particularly evident in labor markets such as Germany's, where credentials regulate access to desirable occupations and thereby contribute to the reproduction of social hierarchies ([Solga and Konietzka, 1999](#); [Bol and Weeden, 2015](#)). Based on prior research and the theoretical framework, we formulate two deductive and one exploratory hypotheses:

The first and central assumption is that individuals with a PhD earn significantly more than those without. Although studies in the German context support this assumption, they are based on relatively old and small datasets.

H1: Individuals with doctoral degrees earn higher incomes than university graduates without one.

Various studies show that women with doctoral degrees earn significantly less than men with doctoral degrees (e.g., [Goldan, 2020](#)). Therefore, we also expect to find evidence of such a gender wage gap in our data. Apart from HCT, ([Goldan, 2020](#), p.9-10) highlights demand-side explanations: discrimination theories, status expectations, and gendered organizations show how biases and organizational norms disadvantage women, sustaining pay gaps despite equal qualifications.

H2: The financial return to earning a PhD is greater for men than for women. Next, we apply decomposition models to explore which wage-relevant characteristics account for the earnings gap between PhD and non-PhD holders. [Trennt and Euler \(2019\)](#) decomposition analysis reveals that, while a large unexplained portion remains, a considerable share of the PhD wage premium can be attributed to structural factors—particularly occupational position, sector of employment, and field of study—whereas characteristics such as gender, age, or region contribute only marginally. Our final hypothesis is exploratory and addresses the influence of occupational fields, which has not yet been tested in the German context.

H3: The wage premium of a PhD varies across occupational fields and is particularly pronounced in specific fields.

This assumption is grounded in the idea that occupational fields differ in their valuation of advanced research skills and specialized expertise. Prior research shows that field-specific human capital strongly shapes wage outcomes

(e.g., Haupt (2016)), and that doctoral graduates benefit particularly in knowledge-intensive or research-oriented occupations (Auriol et al., 2013; Mertens and Rübken, 2013).

3. Empirical analyses

3.1. Data and sample

For our analyses, we use the German *Mikrozensus*, a large-scale, nationally representative survey conducted annually by the Federal Statistical Office of Germany. This survey provides a rich source of detailed demographic, economic, and social data, making it an invaluable resource for empirical research. One of the key strengths of the *Mikrozensus* is its extensive sample size, covering approximately 1% of the German population in each round (with about 70% of the sample available to researchers). This large and representative dataset ensures a high degree of statistical reliability and allows for robust analyses of even relatively small subpopulations, such as individuals with very high levels of education. The *Mikrozensus* collects a broad array of variables, including education level, employment status, income, place of residence, and various regional characteristics. This comprehensive dataset enables researchers to examine complex relationships between education and labor market outcomes. Specifically, for studies focusing on individuals with tertiary education, the dataset offers valuable insights into employment rates, occupational positions, and income levels among the highly educated in Germany. Overall, the *Mikrozensus* is an essential resource for educational researchers seeking to understand labor market integration and socio-economic outcomes among individuals with tertiary education. Its wide coverage and rich detail—underpinned by the legal obligation of participation—make it a cornerstone of evidence-based policy analysis. To enhance the statistical power of our analyses, we pool data from multiple survey rounds. Specifically, we include data from the 2018, 2019, 2021, and 2022 rounds. The 2020 round is excluded, as it was the most significantly affected by the global COVID-19 pandemic.² Until 2020, the survey was primarily conducted face-to-face; since then, respondents have also had the option to complete it online.

The overall sample ($N = 2,506,002$), is restricted to meet the specific requirements of our research. First, we include only individuals who have completed a tertiary education degree—namely, a bachelor’s, master’s, or PhD—reducing the sample to 385,954 observations. It is important to note that the analytical sample excludes individuals with any other

²Due to the exceptionally high unit-nonresponse of about 35% in the 2020 round, the statistical federal office cautions about the usage of this round (<https://www.gesis.org/missy/metadata/MZ/2020>). Rounds before 2018 are excluded as the coding of educational levels in the ISCED has changed, making a harmonization challenging and potentially less reliable.

form of educational qualification. Second, we restrict the sample to individuals aged 25 to 65 ($N = 303,336$). This age criterion serves several purposes. Given that completing a PhD typically requires at least three years beyond a master’s degree, age 25 represents a realistic lower boundary for individuals who may have earned a doctoral degree. Additionally, the upper limit of 65 aligns with typical retirement age, ensuring the sample focuses on individuals actively participating in the labor market (the median age when finishing a PhD is 31 years in Germany, see (BuWiK, 2025, p.95)). As we are interested in income from dependent employment, we focus on this population and exclude retirees. As this age is usually between 63 and 67 in Germany, 65 seems like a reasonable upper bound (Deutsche Rentenversicherung, 2023). Third, only individuals are retained who are employed at the time of the survey ($N = 172,830$). They must be employed by an employer (self-employed individuals are excluded) and have a full-time contract (either permanent or fixed-term; at least 30 hours of regular working time per week). Lastly, we remove observations with missing values on any of the relevant covariates, which gives the final sample size of 163,454 individuals.

3.2. Variables and operationalization

Income is self-reported by respondents at the time of the survey and refers to total personal net income—that is, after-tax income from all sources.³ The income variable is ordinal in nature, as individuals are asked to select the income category that best represents their monthly earnings. Depending on the specific survey round, up to 24 distinct income categories are available. To construct a harmonized income variable, we assign the midpoint of the selected category as the respondent’s income. For example, if a respondent selects the category “€2,000 to €2,250,” we assign a value of €2,125. For analytical purposes, this continuous income measure is then log-transformed using the natural logarithm, a common approach in income analyses to account for right-skewed distributions and to interpret percentage differences in regression models (Ermini and Hendry, 2008). This transformation serves multiple purposes. First, it removes the skewness and results in an approx. normally distributed variable, which can ease statistical inference. Second, and more importantly, it accounts for outliers and makes the interpretation of results more meaningful. For example, an additional income of €500 is substantial for a person earning €2,000, but far less relevant for

³The *Mikrozensus* provides information about the income from the main dependent employment only for a subsample of about 45% of the survey, which would reduce statistical power massively. Our tests have shown that this variable is highly correlated with the income variable (all sources), available for the entire sample (Spearman’s $\rho > .93$), hence we opted for the variable offering much more analytical insight.

someone already earning €8,000. A linear model does not account for this. With the log transformation, changes can be interpreted as percentage differences rather than absolute differences, which is advantageous. The individual's education level is coded into a three-category variable. The first category includes bachelor's degrees—awarded by universities or universities of applied sciences—as well as equivalent qualifications such as the Diplom (FH), corresponding to ISCED level 640 (Federal Institute for Vocational Education and Training, 2025). Vocational degrees classified as ISCED 650, even if formally equivalent to a bachelor's degree, are excluded. The second category includes individuals with a master's degree (ISCED 740) or equivalent qualifications, such as Diplom (Universität), Magister, or state examinations (Staatsexamen) required for professions like teaching, medicine, pharmacy, or law. The third category comprises individuals holding a doctoral degree or PhD, corresponding to ISCED level 800. Gender is coded as a binary variable (men = 0, women = 1). Age is available as a continuous variable but is recoded into five-year age bands. While this introduces some coarseness, it serves two purposes: first, it facilitates the identification of non-linear effects when used as a categorical variable, which is particularly relevant given that income is the dependent variable; second, broader bins enhance the statistical power of each group, even in a large dataset like the *Mikrozensus*, thereby providing more robust estimates. Weekly working hours are self-reported and restricted to values between 30 and 65 hours. Based on their distribution, we recoded this variable into five categories: 30–35 hours, 36–39 hours, 40 hours, 41–45 hours, and 46–65 hours. These values reflect actual hours worked, not contractual working hours.

Occupational status is classified using the ISCO-08 system at the three-digit level (Federal Institute for Vocational Education and Training, 2025). This strikes a balance between granularity and the number of observations available per category. The federal state of employment is included as a categorical variable with 16 values, reflecting the German federal states. It refers to the location of the respondent's workplace, which may differ from their place of residence. Citizenship is coded into three categories: German, non-German European, and other nationalities. The size of the respondent's place of residence is categorized into five groups: fewer than 5,000 residents; 5,000–19,999; 20,000–99,999; 100,000–499,999; and 500,000 or more. Employer size is coded into six categories based on the number of employees: up to 10; 11–19; 20–49; 50–249; 250–499; and 500 or more. Respondents also indicate whether they work in the public sector (e.g., as civil servants or in public institutions). Employment contract type is recorded as either permanent or fixed-term (temporary). Finally, we include an indicator of leadership status, defined as holding a managerial

role with decision-making authority over personnel, budgets, and strategic matters.

3.3. Strategy of analysis

To address our research questions, we estimate a series of ordinary least squares (OLS) regression models. The primary explanatory variables are gender, type of tertiary education (bachelor's, master's, PhD), and age, including their interactions in more advanced predictive models. In addition, we incorporate a set of fixed effects and control variables. This approach allows us to move beyond descriptive wage comparisons and present adjusted estimates. It is important to emphasize that the inclusion of control variables in our models is not aimed to identify causal effects. Estimating causal relationships would require accounting for potential confounding variables that influence both educational attainment and income—such as family background, cognitive ability, or genetic predispositions. As the *Mikrozensus* does not include detailed information on parental education or occupation, cognitive ability, or genetic data, causal inference is beyond the scope of this study. Nonetheless, controlling for relevant covariates enhances comparability between individuals by accounting for observable differences. This approach is analogous to the computation of adjusted gender wage gaps. For instance, while variables such as leadership position or occupational field are not causes of gender, their inclusion helps explain part of the association between gender and wages.

The following variables are included in the adjusted models: actual weekly working hours, federal state of employment, occupational classification (ISCO-08, three-digit level), leadership position, public sector employment, fixed-term contract, employer size, size of the place of residence, and survey round (2018, 2019, 2021, 2022). Including the survey round not only captures temporal effects such as inflation or broader economic shifts but also controls for potential differences in survey implementation over time. To explore model robustness and the incremental explanatory power of covariates, we estimate nested models. The baseline model includes only gender, educational attainment, age, and survey round. The fully adjusted model incorporates all additional control variables. Given that the dependent variable—wages—is log-transformed, we report exponentiated regression coefficients, which can be interpreted as percentage differences in income. In the second part of the analysis, we include an interaction term between gender and educational level to examine whether the wage premium associated with a PhD differs between men and women. To facilitate interpretation, we present results graphically rather than through raw regression output. Similarly, for the advanced prediction models, we rely on visual displays of predicted wages to illustrate interac-

tion effects and adjusted differences across groups. After this first, mostly descriptive overview, we would like to explain why a PhD offers financial benefits. To achieve this, we report a mediation or decomposition analysis. First, a baseline model is computed, including only gender, educational level, and age (and *Mikrozensus* round). When a new variable (for example, working time) is added to this baseline model, the coefficients of the education variable can change. If this happens, we regard this as a mediation effect (as working time is a potential consequence of educational level, not precursor). The absolute percentage change of the education level coefficient can then be interpreted as the degree of mediation or decomposition. In this analysis, we first test the relevant variables separately (leadership position, size of employer, citizenship, size of place of residence, occupation, federal state, working time, public sector, fixed-term contract)⁴, and finally all together for an overall view. The results are reported graphically, inference is possible utilizing a bootstrap strategy (Efron and Tibshirani, 1994; Bittmann, 2021).

In the last part of the analysis, we would like to investigate whether the effect of a PhD on wages differs by occupational field. To do so, only individuals with either a master's degree or a PhD are retained, and the educational degree variable is binary coded. Then, the interaction term between educational degree and ISCO-08 (3-digit) occupation is included and average marginal effects of a PhD in terms of wages are computed. Doing so lets us check whether a PhD is especially beneficial (or detrimental) in certain fields. The results are presented graphically. All results are computed using Stata 18.0. Various user-written programs are utilized in the analyses, such as `reghdfe` (Correia, 2017), `coefplot` (Jann, 2014), and `crosswalk`⁵. As the data are official and respondents are required by law to participate, the number of genuinely missing values (e.g. refusal or item-nonresponse) is very low. Hence, the data are not imputed but listwise deletion is applied. All analyses include sampling weights provided by the *Mikrozensus* to ensure the highest possible accuracy in representing the overall German population. Whenever applicable, robust standard errors are utilized.⁶

⁴Technically, citizenship is not a consequence of educational level but rather a precursor. However, it can still give valuable insight, for example, to quantify potential effects of discrimination.

⁵<https://github.com/benjann/crosswalk/>

⁶We have also computed the results using cluster standard errors with *Mikrozensus* primary sampling units as clusters. However, as results are virtually identical to the robust ones, we have opted for the latter option.

Figure 1: Distribution of educational qualifications by gender
Source: Mikrozensus 2018/2022, N = 163,454; sampling weights applied.

4. Results

4.1. Descriptive results

To enable a description of the analytical sample, descriptive statistics are reported in the appendix (Table 2). Of the sample, 37% are women. 43% hold a bachelor's degree, 50% a master's degree, and 7.3% a PhD. The median monthly income is about €3,125, and the median age is 41 years. About half of the sample (47%) report working exactly 40 hours per week, which is the standard contract in Germany. Thirty percent work in the public sector, and 22% in a leadership position. About 9% have a fixed-term contract. Figure 1 indicates that, among employees with tertiary education, holding a PhD is slightly more common for men than for women (8% vs. 6%).

4.2. Main regression results

The main results of the OLS regression models are reported in Table 1. In model M1, the mostly descriptive findings are reported. The reference category is individuals with a master's degree. As the coefficient for individuals with a PhD is 1.27, we conclude that they earn about 27% more. Individuals with a bachelor's degree have a coefficient of 0.92, meaning that they earn about 8% less. Women earn 20% less than men, which indicates a rather severe (unadjusted) gender pay gap, even for tertiary educated women. However, this gap corresponds very well to previous reports (e.g., Goldan (2021)). The second model (M2) adds all control variables and hence reports the adjusted effect of having obtained a PhD. Here, the coefficient has reduced to 1.117, meaning that individuals with a PhD still earn about 12% more than those with a master's degree, even if they work the same hours, at the same place, in a similar occupation.¹ In the adjusted model, the

gender-pay gap has decreased to about 14% female disadvantage. R^2 has increased drastically by adding these additional variables, from about 24% to 44%. Still, even in this rather advanced model, more than 50% of the total variation in wages remains unexplained, indicating a rather heterogeneous and complex landscape.

As an additional robustness check, we have computed a Heckman selection model. As some individuals are not active in the labor market at the time of the survey, they do not report a wage. However, participation in the labor market is not random but based on various other factors. The Heckman model includes a total of 220,120 individuals (included in this version are all respondents who do not report a wage or work fewer than 30 hours per week; still excluded are individuals who are self-employed). Our results indicate that selection into the outcome is present but rather weak ($\rho = 0.053$; $\lambda = 0.019$). The PhD advantage is 11.46%, which is almost identical to the results from the main model (even as we include marriage status and number of individuals in the household in the selection model). Summarized, selection into the outcome does not bias our findings. Complete tables are available upon request.

Figure 2 reports whether educational degrees have differential effects for men and women on wages. The left side of the graph compares individuals with a bachelor's degree to those with a master's degree, both in an adjusted and unadjusted version. It becomes clear that in the adjusted version, both men and women with a bachelor's degree earn about 5% less than those with a master's degree. For the comparison between master's degree and PhD, the (adjusted) benefit is about 13% for men and 10% for women; the exact difference is 2.66 percentage points [95% CI: 0.99; 4.29; $p = 0.002$]. Due to the very large sample size, this difference is statistically significant, yet as the effect sizes are quite similar, we argue that obtaining a PhD has rather similar benefits for both men and women.

Next, we examine predicted incomes. To do so, we compute the adjusted model and add a three-way interaction term between gender, educational degree, and age. We then predict wages for all possible combinations and plot the results in Figure 3. Wages are rather similar up to age 30; afterwards, incomes diverge by educational level. Individuals with a PhD show the steepest increase over time. The most pronounced differences occur from age 45 onward, where individuals with a PhD have the highest incomes by a wide margin. Overall trends are similar for men and women, yet it is clear that, on average, women earn considerably less than men. When interpreting these results, it is important to keep in mind that this is a cross-sectional analysis, as no panel data are available. Hence, we only observe descriptions and cannot conclude that having a PhD is the causal factor behind wage gains with age.

Figure 2: Adjusted and unadjusted education coefficients by gender
Source: Mikrozensus 2018/2022, $N = 163,454$; sampling weights applied. Reported are exponentiated OLS coefficients. 95% confidence intervals included, based on robust standard errors. Unadjusted models control for age and *Mikrozensus* round. Adjusted models also add civil servant, leadership position, size of employer, citizenship, size of place of residence, federal state, working hours, fixed-term contract, and occupation. Reported p-values represent statistical significance of gender differences.

As the data cannot distinguish between age and cohort effects, it remains unclear whether the exceptionally positive developments for PhD holders are a consequence of age (i.e., greater experience with increasing age) or a cohort effect (i.e., people who are now 50 entered the labor market under particularly favorable conditions, which still shape their current income situation).

4.3. Decomposition analysis

As described earlier, the decomposition or mediation analysis tests whether certain consequences of educational attainment can explain why different degrees are associated with different wages. As the previous analysis has shown that wage differences by degree are quite similar for men and women, we compute a single model including both genders. The mediation contribution of each relevant variable is first tested individually and finally a model is presented in which all influences are considered together. Results are presented graphically in Figure 4. The largest single influence is occupation in the labor market (ISCO 3-digit classification). This means that once occupation is added to the baseline model (which only includes age, gender, and *Mikrozensus* round), the coefficients for educational attainment are reduced by about 28%. In other words, the occupation in the labor market explains about 28% of the advantage of a PhD (and the disadvantage of a BA) in terms of wages. One can conclude that individuals with a PhD work in different occupations than those with a master's degree (the association between occupation and education is .385, Cramér's V), and that this occupational sort-

Table 1: OLS Regression Results

	M1	M2
Log. total net personal income		
Master's degree	Ref.	Ref.
Bachelor's degree	0.916*** [0.912, 0.920]	0.944*** [0.941, 0.948]
PhD	1.268*** [1.257, 1.279]	1.117*** [1.108, 1.126]
Female	0.797*** [0.793, 0.800]	0.858*** [0.854, 0.861]
Age group		
40/45	Ref.	Ref.
25/29	0.711*** [0.705, 0.717]	0.766*** [0.760, 0.772]
30/34	0.801*** [0.794, 0.807]	0.836*** [0.830, 0.842]
35/39	0.901*** [0.894, 0.909]	0.921*** [0.915, 0.928]
45/49	1.081*** [1.071, 1.091]	1.068*** [1.060, 1.076]
50/54	1.102*** [1.092, 1.112]	1.082*** [1.074, 1.090]
55/59	1.085*** [1.075, 1.095]	1.073*** [1.065, 1.081]
60/65	1.037*** [1.027, 1.048]	1.055*** [1.046, 1.064]
Working hours per week		
40		Ref.
30 to 35		0.915*** [0.907, 0.922]
36 to 39		0.947*** [0.942, 0.952]
41 to 45		1.049*** [1.044, 1.054]
46 to 65		1.163*** [1.155, 1.171]
Public sector		0.983*** [0.978, 0.988]
Leadership position		1.196*** [1.189, 1.202]
Fixed-term contract		0.797*** [0.790, 0.804]
Size of company		
Up to 10		Ref.
11 to 19		1.059*** [1.048, 1.071]
20 to 49		1.106*** [1.095, 1.116]
50 to 249		1.163*** [1.153, 1.174]
250 to 499		1.217*** [1.205, 1.229]
More than 500		1.311*** [1.300, 1.323]
Citizenship		
German citizen		Ref.
EU Citizen		0.982*** [0.973, 0.992]
Other Citizen		0.953*** [0.944, 0.963]
Size of place of residence		
Up to 5k		Ref.
5k/20k		1.000 [0.993, 1.007]
20k/100k		1.004 [0.997, 1.012]
100k/500k		0.986*** [0.979, 0.993]
More than 500k		1.022*** [1.014, 1.030]
ISCO-08 3-digit occupation	No	Yes
Federal state of employer	No	Yes
Mikrozensus round	Yes	Yes
Constant	3738*** [3712, 3765]	2908*** [2874, 2943]
Observations	163,454	163,454
R ²	0.225	0.452

Source: Mikrozensus 2018/2022, sampling weights applied. Reported are exponentiated OLS coefficients. 95% confidence intervals included, based on robust standard errors. * p < 0.05, ** p < 0.01, *** p < 0.001

Figure 3: Predicted (adjusted) incomes by gender, age, and educational qualification Source: Mikrozensus 2018/2022, N = 163,454; sampling weights applied. 95% confidence intervals included, based on robust standard errors. Predictions adjusted for Mikrozensus round, civil servant, leadership position, size of employer, citizenship, size of place of residence, federal state, working hours, fixed-term contract, and occupation.

ing explains part of the financial benefits. The second most important factor is working hours, which alone accounts for about 17 % of the wage differences. The third and fourth most important factors are leadership position and employer size (both about 11%). All other factors have very little explanatory power in terms of mediation.⁷

Interestingly, the result for fixed-term contracts are negative by about -10%.⁸ This means that PhD holders are more likely than other tertiary graduates to have non-permanent jobs, which are associated with lower incomes (see Table 2, M2). This leads to a negative coefficient, implying that employees with a PhD would earn even more if they were in permanent positions. When taking all influences together, about 48% of the wage differences between individuals with different tertiary degrees are accounted for. Note that the individual

⁷Not only do PhD graduates work in different occupations but also in better ones. While not focus of this study, based on the occupation in the labor market, one can derive the ISEI (International Socio-Economic Index of Occupational Status), which is a continuous measurement (values range between 10 and 89) of socio-economic status; higher values indicating a higher status. When we compute a (fully adjusted) regression model with ISEI as the dependent variable, employees with a PhD have, on average, a 6.3 point advantage (95% CI: 6.1; 6.5) compared to employees with a Master's degree.

⁸While not quite intuitive, negative effects are possible as well. This means that, as soon as this variable is accounted for, the effect of education becomes larger. To explain this, consider public sector. Individuals with a PhD work more often in the public sector than individuals with a master's degree, yet average incomes are lower in the public sector, leading to a negative mediation result.

factors are necessarily correlated (as one would expect), since 48% is less than the sum of all individual factors. To provide additional context, Figure 6 in the appendix shows the associations between educational levels and various explanatory factors.

4.4. Occupation analysis

Finally, we statistically test whether obtaining a PhD is especially beneficial in certain occupational fields. To do so, all individuals with a bachelor's degree are removed from this analysis. The main adjusted model is then adapted by introducing an interaction term between the PhD variable and the occupational field variable. Subsequently, predicted wage differences are computed and reported in Figure 5. Although the sample is relatively large, the large number of occupational fields means that effect sizes are not always very stable. Hence, we report only fields (ISCO 3-digit classification) with at least 30 individuals holding a PhD (and at least 60 individuals in total) and with a coefficient that is statistically significant at the 5% level. The highest wage premiums for PhD graduates are found among finance professionals (+27%), legal professionals (+25%), and professional services managers (+21%). Notable and reliable premiums are also observed for life sciences professionals (+14%), engineering professionals (+9%), software developers (+8%), and medical doctors

Figure 4: Decomposition (mediation) of the education effect Source: Mikrozensus 2018/2022, N = 163,454; sampling weights applied. 95% confidence intervals included, based on 1,000 BC-bootstrap resamples. All models adjusted for Mikrozensus round, gender, and age.

(+6%). For additional insight, we provide a complete table with all ISCO codes in the supplemental materials.

As a final analytical step, we demonstrate that PhD wage premiums are present across a wide variety of occupational fields. To visualize this, we show Figure 7 in the appendix, where the wage premium is plotted against the ISCO-08 code (first two digits). In this analysis, all estimates are included, regardless of statistical significance. The results indicate that the PhD premium is evident in a broad range of occupational fields. From this, we conclude that PhD premium is a general finding rather than one specific to certain occupational or educational fields.

5. Discussion

In line with previous publications, our results clearly indicate that a PhD pays off financially, as graduates report higher wages, on average, than comparable graduates with a master's degree. Consequently, we accept hypothesis 1, which predicted a PhD premium. This wage premium differs by gender. The difference amounts to about 2.7 percentage points in the fully adjusted model. Since this difference is statistically significant at the 1% level, we accept hypothesis 2. While we also observe a very large and concerning gender pay gap, as many other studies have already shown (Goldan, 2021), we argue that the PhD-specific gender pay gap is not as pronounced. This suggests that the highest form of education is beneficial to both genders and that pursuing a PhD makes sense for both.

What clearly goes beyond previous studies is the long-term development of income in relation to PhD attainment. We observe the largest income differentials from age 45 on-

ward. While the dataset cannot provide information about individual trajectories, we suggest that these PhD wage premiums, which grow over the course of careers, may be substantial. We can think of two possible explanations. Either, the additional premium is purely cumulative and is a result of the earlier and potentially better promotions employees with a PhD receive. An alternative explanation may be that holders of a PhD cluster in the most beneficial positions, which are not necessarily related to leadership (as this aspect has been controlled for), yet come with additional wage premiums over the course of a career. In any case, even if the data allow no causal conclusions, the descriptive advantage PhD graduates have with age is huge and requires additional research for a better understanding.

When we turn to explaining the PhD wage premiums, occupational field is the single most relevant explanatory factor. This underlines that PhD graduates earn more because they work in different, higher-paid occupations. This gives some support to credentials labor market theories, as there might be restrictions on access to certain positions and fields. A second piece of evidence is that PhD graduates more often hold leadership positions. Apparently, a PhD can serve as an entry key to such valuable positions, either because graduates are actually more productive or because access is restricted and a PhD serves as a relevant signal. Graduates also tend to work for larger employers, which typically offer higher wages. However, one intriguing aspect is that, even though our model did include many relevant explanatory variables, more than 50% of the PhD wage premium remains unexplained. This may mean that we are not able to quantify certain aspects,

Figure 5: PhD wage premiums by occupation in the labor market Source: Mikrozensus 2018/2022, $N > 60$ for each ISCO category; sampling weights applied. Reported are exponentiated OLS coefficients (printed on the upper end of the confidence intervals). 95% confidence intervals included, based on robust standard errors. Adjusted for gender, age, Mikrozensus round, civil servant, leadership position, size of employer, citizenship, size of place of residence, federal state, working hours, fixed-term contract.

such as productivity, in detail. Alternatively, it may indicate that the explanation lies in the PhD itself: simply holding a doctorate signals value that prompts employers to pay more. This also strongly relates to the final part of our analyses, where individuals within narrow occupational positions are compared. For example, we demonstrate that in finance professions, employees with a PhD earn, on average, about 27% more than those with a master's degree. As this model is fully adjusted for gender, age, working time, place of residence, and leadership position (and more factors), the question remains why these employees still earn more. They essentially work under the same conditions, for the same employers, in the same jobs. Still, PhD graduates profit considerably. It seems unlikely that these individuals are up to 27% more productive than others, given the control conditions. Hence, the question remains as to why the surplus exists. As we find 23 occupational fields with substantial and statistically significant PhD wage premiums, we believe that this is a general phenomenon, especially since the occupations are diverse and cannot easily be reduced to a certain branch or specialty. Finally, we accept Hypothesis 3, which predicted that the PhD wage premium varies by field. To summarize: a PhD is beneficial in a wide range of occupational positions, yet in some occupations, it is even more worthy.

Lastly, we would like to discuss the limitations of our study. First, since only cross-sectional data are available, we cannot estimate causal effects or effects of individual life courses. This is especially relevant when interpreting results from income predictions across the life course. It remains

unclear whether the increasing wages for the PhD group are due to the PhD or caused by other influences, such as cohort effects. Second, it must be noted that only the current position is considered in our data. For example, a respondent who held a permanent contract for ten years but became unemployed at the time of the *Mikrozensus* survey would not be included in the analyses. Moreover, the *Mikrozensus* does not provide individual labor market histories. While this limits our analyses, we do not expect systematic bias resulting from this limitation as unemployment, in general, was not a central societal issue in the years from 2018 to 2022 (even in the post-COVID phase).

6. Conclusions

Our findings suggest that attaining the highest level of education—a PhD—can be a worthwhile investment. Drawing on comprehensive German official statistics with a very large sample size, we show that individuals with a PhD earn significantly higher incomes, both in descriptive terms and within fully adjusted models. In other words, even when comparing individuals who are similar in age, experience, place of residence, and occupational position, those with a PhD consistently earn more than their counterparts holding a master's degree. Importantly, the financial advantage of a PhD appears to be similar for both men and women. Notably, the largest income gains tend to appear after several years in the labor market, suggesting that the returns to a PhD may increase over time.

To better understand the underlying mechanisms, our analyses indicate that the income premium associated with a PhD is largely attributable to differences in occupational placement, longer working hours, greater likelihood of holding leadership roles, and employment in larger organizations. Taken together, these results offer important insights into the value of higher education in Germany and highlight the enduring economic benefits associated with doctoral-level qualifications. As an outlook, we especially welcome replication studies from different countries to test whether these results are unique to Germany or not.

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Figure 7: PhD wage premiums by occupational position in the labor market Source: Mikrozensus 2018/2022; sampling weights applied. 1 = Managers, 2 = Professionals, 3 = Technicians, 4 = Clerical support Workers, 5 = Service and sales workers, 6 = Skilled agricultural, forestry and fishery workers, 7 = Craft and related trade workers, 8 = Plant and machine operators, and assemblers, 9 = Elementary occupations.

8. Appendix

Figure 6: Associations between educational qualification and various predictors of wage Source: Mikrozensus 2018/2022, N = 163,454; sampling weights applied. Large employer = 500 or more employees. SD not shown for binary variables.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Mean	Median	SD	Min	Max
Total net personal income	3530.7	3125	2061.5	75	25000
Log. total net personal income	8.05	8.05	0.48	4.32	10.1
Highest tertiary degree					
Bachelor's degree	0.43	0	0.50	0	1
Master's degree	0.50	0	0.50	0	1
PhD	0.073	0	0.26	0	1
Female respondent	0.37	0	0.48	0	1
Age (cont.)	42.3	41	11.1	25	65
Age categories					
25–29	0.14	0	0.34	0	1
30–34	0.19	0	0.39	0	1
35–39	0.15	0	0.35	0	1
40–44	0.12	0	0.32	0	1
45–49	0.10	0	0.31	0	1
50–54	0.12	0	0.33	0	1
55–59	0.11	0	0.31	0	1
60–65	0.077	0	0.27	0	1
Working in the public sector	0.30	0	0.46	0	1
Working in a leadership position	0.21	0	0.41	0	1
Fixed-term position	0.086	0	0.28	0	1
Size of company					
Up to 10	0.068	0	0.25	0	1
11–19	0.068	0	0.25	0	1
20–49	0.13	0	0.34	0	1
50–249	0.27	0	0.44	0	1
250–499	0.11	0	0.31	0	1
500+	0.35	0	0.48	0	1
Citizenship					
German citizen	0.88	1	0.33	0	1
EU citizen	0.059	0	0.23	0	1
Other citizen	0.062	0	0.24	0	1
Size of place of residence					
Below 5k	0.081	0	0.27	0	1
5k–20k	0.21	0	0.41	0	1
20k–100k	0.21	0	0.41	0	1
100k–500k	0.21	0	0.40	0	1
500k+	0.29	0	0.45	0	1
Working hours per week					
30–35	0.056	0	0.23	0	1
36–39	0.16	0	0.37	0	1
40	0.47	0	0.50	0	1
41–45	0.18	0	0.38	0	1
46–65	0.13	0	0.33	0	1
Observations	163454				

Source: Mikrozensus 2018/2022, sampling weights applied.